

*Toppling a market friendly regime: the role of repression
and economic growth*

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During the the 21st century we have observed a revival of the interest in the transitions toward democracy, or toward more representative regimes, across the Middle East, Eastern Europe or the African continent. Accordingly, the academic literature responded by analyzing the political and economic determinants of these processes (see e.g. Acemoglu and Robinson (2009), whose ultimate intricacies must be explored empirically (see e.g. Stephan and Chenoweth (2008)). However, with this piece, we aim to contribute by searching theoretically for some determinants related to economic growth and the (macroeconomic) business cycle.

Our questions could be formulated as follows: is economic growth prone to strengthen the progressive protests or, on the contrary, is poverty and absolute deprivation responsible for this sort of transformations? To what extent it is possible to predict in economic terms such disruptive political change? To that purpose, we use a model inspired by Lohmann (1994), about the possibilities opened by productivity growth on the success of the working class' vindications.

Let us consider a country ruled by a market-friendly dictatorship, which is threatened by a collectivist opposition. The members of the opposition will try to topple the dictatorship, expropriate the returns to the productive capital and distribute the existing resources among the working class. In order to achieve this goal, they need to demonstrate and take to the streets. Given the existing levels of repression; and a certain capacity to influence the international opinion, the necessary turnout of the demonstrations needs to be k' people out of a population of L individuals.

The production function in this country $(Y = K^\beta (AL)^{1-\beta})$ combines an aggregate stock of productive capital (K) and some efficiency units of labor (AL). We will under-

take our comparative statics exercise with respect to the parameter A , trying to understand how economic growth can affect the magnitude of the protests and the chances to topple the government. It is possible to assume that, in case of a revolutionary demise of the dictatorship, the whole national output (Y) would accrue to the labor force, whereas otherwise every worker would receive a wage rate (w) determined by a competitive labor market.

Let us denote by $P(\hat{C})$ and \hat{C} the probability that the dictatorial regime will be toppled and the probability that any citizen will decide to demonstrate, respectively. Then the stock of productive capital results from the following maximization problem, faced by the capitalists:

$$Max_K \left(1 - P(\hat{C})\right) \beta K^\beta (AL)^{1-\beta} - K \quad (1)$$

We have implicitly assumed in (1) that one unit of final output can be transformed into a unit of capital. Moreover, in equilibrium,

$$K = AL \left[\left(1 - P(\hat{C})\right) \beta^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{1-\beta}}$$

$$\frac{Y}{L} = A \left[\left(1 - P(\hat{C})\right) \beta^2 \right]^{\frac{\beta}{1-\beta}}$$

$$w = (1 - \beta) \frac{Y}{L} \quad (2)$$

Our results will be derived from the interplay of the workers' protests and the capital owners' decisions on production. We need to consider that demonstrating is costly for every participant, due to the potential repression. Every individual's ex-post cost will be idiosyncratic, and ex-ante it will follow a uniform probability distribution within the support $[0, 1]$.

This implies that the cutoff value of the cost that makes him indifferent (between showing up or not) is also equal to his ex-ante probability of protesting (\hat{C}). If the dictatorship is (is not) finally toppled, our individual will get $\frac{Y}{L}(w)$, together with the above mentioned cost in case of participation in the protests.

Let us denote by k to the number of people who turn out in the demonstrations. The threshold value of the cost (\hat{C}) will be determined by the following indifference condition between protesting or not:

$$(1 - \beta) \frac{Y}{L} \sum_{k=0}^{k'-1} \binom{L-1}{k} \hat{C}^k (1 - \hat{C})^{L-k-1} + \frac{Y}{L} \sum_{k=k'}^{L-1} \binom{L-1}{k} \hat{C}^k (1 - \hat{C})^{L-k-1} = \quad (3)$$

Expected payoff if the individual does not participate

$$(1 - \beta) \frac{Y}{L} \sum_{k=0}^{k'-2} \binom{L-1}{k} \hat{C}^k (1 - \hat{C})^{L-k-1} + \frac{Y}{L} \sum_{k=k'-1}^{L-1} \binom{L-1}{k} \hat{C}^k (1 - \hat{C})^{L-k-1} - \hat{C} \quad (4)$$

Expected payoff if the individual participates

In the last equation (4) many terms will cancel out. After simplifying and rearranging, we can express the indifference condition as

$$1 = \beta \frac{Y}{L} \binom{L-1}{k'-1} \hat{C}^{k'-2} (1 - \hat{C})^{L-k'} \quad (5)$$

From (2), we can restate (5) in equilibrium as follows:

$$1 = \beta^{\frac{1+\beta}{1-\beta}} (1 - P(\hat{C}))^{\frac{\beta}{1-\beta}} A \binom{L-1}{k'-1} \hat{C}^{k'-2} (1 - \hat{C})^{L-k'} \quad (6)$$

Since we know that

$$(1 - P(\hat{C})) = \sum_{k=0}^{k'-1} \binom{L}{k} \hat{C}^k (1 - \hat{C})^{L-k} \quad (7)$$

then, by plugging (7) into (6), we can obtain that

$$\beta^{\frac{1+\beta}{1-\beta}} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{k'-1} \binom{L}{k} \hat{C}^k (1 - \hat{C})^{L-k} \right)^{\frac{\beta}{1-\beta}} A \binom{L-1}{k'-1} \hat{C}^{k'-2} (1 - \hat{C})^{L-k'} = 1 \quad (8)$$

This last equation implicitly characterizes \hat{C} . Therefore, we could apply the implicit function theorem to derive $\frac{d\hat{C}}{dA}$, which is our final goal. By differentiating in (8) with respect to A , it is possible to come up with the following expression:

$$\frac{1}{A} + \frac{(k'-2) \frac{d\hat{C}}{dA}}{\hat{C}} - \frac{(L-k') \frac{d\hat{C}}{dA}}{(1-\hat{C})} + \left(\frac{\beta}{1-\beta} \right) \frac{d\hat{C}}{dA} \frac{\left(\sum_{k=0}^{k'-1} \binom{L}{k} \hat{C}^{k-1} (1-\hat{C})^{L-k-1} (k-L\hat{C}) \right) \hat{C}^{k-1} (1-\hat{C})^{L-k-1}}{\sum_{k=0}^{k'-1} \binom{L}{k} \hat{C}^k (1-\hat{C})^{L-k}} = 0 \quad (9)$$

This last equation (9) is not easy to handle analytically and should be explored numerically. However, it is still possible to learn from the model if we analyze two extreme situations: the case in which all the population needs to turn out to topple the government ($k' \rightarrow L$), and the polar case in which a single participant is enough to precipitate the end of the regime ($k' \rightarrow 1$).

Let us analyze in turn both cases. If $k' \rightarrow L$ then either the regime is very repressive or the demonstrations have no international impact on the public opinion. Consequently, $P(\hat{C}) = \hat{C}^L$ and therefore our equation (6) now reads

$$1 = \beta^{\frac{1+\beta}{1-\beta}} (1 - \hat{C}^L)^{\frac{\beta}{1-\beta}} A \hat{C}^{L-2} \quad (10)$$

If we apply the implicit function theorem to (10) then it is straightforward to get that

$$\frac{d\hat{C}}{dA} = \frac{1}{A \left(\left(\frac{\beta}{1-\beta} \right) L \frac{\hat{C}^{L-1}}{1-\hat{C}^L} - \left(\frac{L-2}{\hat{C}} \right) \right)} \quad (11)$$

The right hand side of (11) will be then negative if

$$\left(\frac{\beta}{1-\beta} \right) \frac{\hat{C}^L}{1-\hat{C}^L} < \frac{L-2}{L} \quad (12)$$

and that condition will hold for sure if the population in the country is sufficiently large, i.e. if $L \rightarrow \infty$; since then the limit on the left hand side will be zero and on the right hand side will be one. As a result, we can state that for a sufficiently large country, when $k' \rightarrow L$ (because of too much repression or isolation) $\frac{d\hat{C}}{dA} < 0$. That is, more economic growth will induce lower participation in the protests and lower chances to topple the regime. Only when the economic prospects are extremely negative, will the population decide to take the risk and demonstrate massively.

On the other hand, if $k' \rightarrow 1$ then necessarily $P(\hat{C}) = 1 - (1 - \hat{C})^L$ and by (2) and (5) we can conclude that

$$1 = \beta^{\frac{1+\beta}{1-\beta}} (1 - \hat{C})^{L \left(\frac{\beta}{1-\beta} \right) + L - 1} \left(\frac{A}{\hat{C}} \right) \quad (13)$$

By inspecting the last expression (13), we can see that necessarily $\frac{d\hat{C}}{dA} > 0$, since a rise A must be compensated by another rise in \hat{C} to preserve the equality. This implies that economic growth will promote the revolt and the toppling of the government, since the working class will be able to appropriate more resources. Therefore, we can summarize our findings with the following proposition.

For a sufficiently large country, if the level of repression and / or international isolation is extreme ($k' \rightarrow L$) then economic growth will lower the chances to topple the regime. Exactly the opposite will happen if $k' \rightarrow 1$: people will tend to demonstrate more intensely the higher economic growth is.

Figure 1. $L = 4$; $\beta = 0.7$; $kt = 2$;

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